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The Influence of Adhocracy Culture on Corporate Performance: An Examination of Hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The state of a country's hospitality sector regulates the progress of its inhabitants' wellbeing and quality of life. The Nigerian hospitality industry is challenged with matters that result in deprived service delivery. Therefore, this study seeks to ascertain the result of adhocracy culture on the performance of hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study was focused on resource-based view theory. Together descriptive and explanatory research projects were used. The study targeted 20 hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria. All the hotels were comprised in the study and consequently, it was a census. The unit of observation included 10 departmental heads from each hotel. A total of 200 respondents were anticipated to contribute to the study. Structured questionnaire was used to obtain primary data. Pilot data was used to measure the questionnaire's reliability. Frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviation were used in descriptive statistical analysis. Inferential statistics were used to determine how variables were related. It consisted of correlation and regression analysis to assess the relationship between the independent and dependent variable. The findings of the correlation analysis found out that adhocracy culture had a positive and significant relationship with corporate performance ($r=0.640$, $p=0.000$). Further, regression output indicated that adhocracy culture had a positive and significant effect on firm performance ($\beta=.719$, $p=0.000$).

Keywords: Adhocracy culture, Corporate Performance, Hospitalities.

Introduction

The evaluation of the corporation's performance can be systematically assessed through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies. According to the findings of Berberoglu (2018), the implementation of a comprehensive work system can effectively facilitate the attainment of a company's objectives. These objectives may include substantial increases in market share, impressive financial performance, substantial income generation, and the ability to sustain favourable outcomes within a specific timeframe. Al Hammadi and Hussain (2019) propose that an operation can be perceived as a corporate strategy that significantly impacts the productivity of employees inside an organisation, both in tangible and metaphorical terms.

A multitude of scholars have embraced diverse measures for assessing organisational performance within the hospitality sector. The year 2014. Acar & Acar proposed a theoretical framework for assessing corporate success,

Original Article

encompassing several factors such as people diversity, levels of staff arrogance, representation of underprivileged individuals, customer complaints, service satisfaction, and financial performance of new services. Amolo (2018) conducted a study in which the measurement of organisational performance was based on the efficient allocation of resources and the provision of exceptional customer service. Omondi (2016) employed the dimensions of quality, affordability, accessibility, and acceptability as operational measures for company performance. This study employed customer satisfaction, organisational behaviour, resource management, employee commitment, and cost-effectiveness as indicators to evaluate the operational performance of hotels.

According to Tseng (2010), an adhocratic culture refers to a work environment that is characterised by diversity, profitability, imagination, and creativity. The identified priorities are the development of novel products and services, adaptability to modifications, expansion, and achievement (Nwile, & Kayii 2023; Asaah, Effah, & Sam, 2015). According to Gao (2017), there exists a positive correlation between the presence of an adherent culture and the success of organisations. Fekete and Bocskei (2011) suggest that the adhocratic tradition exerts a significant impact on the economic performance of enterprises. An exemplary illustration of this cultural phenomenon is represented by a digitally-oriented organisation that operates online, characterised by its incorporation of innovative technologies and participation in the new economy (Acar & Acar, 2014). Misigo et al. (2019) characterise an adhocratic community as one that encompasses project expansion, corporate leadership, and the procurement of novel tools. According to Migdadi, Zaid, Yousif, Almestarihi, and Al-Hyari (2017), adhocracy is a cultural framework that promotes conformity, utility, and strategic thinking within organisations, enabling them to flourish under complexity, ambiguity, and information overload. The present study assessed the adhocracy culture by examining its characteristics of flexibility, individual initiative, and resource acquisition.

The primary objective of the government is to provide cost-effective and superior hospitality services to the Nigerian population, as well as to neighbouring nations. This objective is most effectively achieved through the use of hotels located in Rivers State, Nigeria. According to the Ministry of Commerce (MOC, 2019), these establishments play a crucial role within the hospitality industry of the nation. They serve as intermediary facilities that bridge the gap between local regions and nationally recommended hotels, thereby substituting the recommendation hotels of regional establishments.

Furthermore, these establishments function as local centres for providing specific hospitality services, including comprehensive hospitality services and consultations with expert hospitality service providers. Hotels employ a variety of professionals in the hospitality business, such as specialised managers, waitstaff, housekeeping personnel, front desk staff, catering personnel, and professional accountants (MOC, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

The calibre of a nation's hospitality service system is a determining factor in the health and quality of life experienced by its population. Nevertheless, it is widely acknowledged that the Nigerian hotel industry has experienced a decline in revenues ranging from 10% to 18% as a result of limitations in inventory. The act of temporarily residing with acquaintances, relatives, and other individuals outside of one's own residence due to professional or business-related travel, conferences, seminars, workshop trainings, and similar engagements has been linked to instances of discomfort. For example, it is widely assumed that a significant proportion, over 40%, of individuals who are unfamiliar with one another experience dissatisfaction when they are unable to secure lodging due to personal or occupational commitments. Furthermore, according to the provided figures, it can be

Original Article

observed that 8.7% of households belonging to the quintile with the lowest earnings experience a decrease in their housing expenditures. Individuals often seek accommodations that surpass their actual needs due to the subpar minimum standards of care and persistent issues with the recommendation system. These factors subsequently impact the overall functioning of the hospitality system.

A previous investigation revealed a correlation between the performance of a company and its organisational culture. Nevertheless, these analyses reveal numerous gaps in the existing research. The current research is characterised by contextual gaps, as previous investigations (Wambugu, 2014; Indiya, Obura, & Mise, 2018; Misigo, Were, & Odhiambo, 2019) were conducted in dissimilar settings. The research findings and conclusions are deemed inappropriate for inclusion in this report due to the presence of background variances. The aforementioned research mostly emphasised industries other than the hotel sector. Furthermore, other studies highlight theoretical limitations. The study conducted by Omukaga (2016) examined the performance of workers, which is a component of overall business performance. Additionally, there exists a methodological gap. Ngara (2018) was constrained to a certain business. A survey of hotels was conducted for the current study. The study's goal was to evaluate how the adhocracy culture in Rivers State, Nigeria, affected the operation of hotels in light of the aforementioned information gaps.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Resource Based View Theory

The resource-based theory approach, as developed by Barney (1991), posits that companies can be conceptualised as an assemblage of resources that are distributed heterogeneously inside organisations, leading to the persistence of resource disparities across time. Based on the concept, a collection of assets can be employed to symbolise a company. The idea posits that organisations acquire and sustain a competitive advantage by effectively utilising resources and opportunities that would otherwise be inaccessible. The internal administrative components of the organisation had a significant role in its sustained competitive advantage and exceptional operational outcomes. The core prediction of this theory posits that the utilisation of specialised and unique administrative tools and abilities can lead to consistently improved performance.

The concept prompts inquiry into the strategies that firms might employ to acquire and sustain these advantages. The concept also underscores the significance of achieving long-term benefits. As noted by Kapelko (2006), an organisation can attain a lasting competitive advantage by effectively using these resources during the production of its commodities. According to Madhani (2010), the concept entails the exploration and extrapolation of internal resources to develop strategies aimed at attaining a sustainable competitive advantage. Based on the hypothesis proposed by Barney (1991), a company's competitive advantage is derived from its possession of distinctive and highly valued resources that are difficult to imitate or substitute, and in certain instances, constitute the entirety of the firm's capital. In order to attain enduring advantages and strategic goals, it is imperative for organisations to ensure the availability and utilisation of appropriate tools for planned initiatives (Collis, 1995).

The relevance of the resource perspective to this study stems from its exploration of the significance of corporate resources in enhancing operational effectiveness. The primary focus of this study is to examine the utilisation of adhocracy culture as an internal resource by organisations in order to optimise operational efficiency. From a theoretical standpoint, it can be argued that an organization's adhocracy culture possesses inherent value,

Original Article

potentially contributing to its overall success. Consequently, it can be inferred that using adhocracy culture as a strategic asset has the potential to enhance organisational effectiveness.

Empirical Review

The study conducted by Yesil and Kaya in 2013 examined the impact of corporate culture on the financial performance of Turkish enterprises. The study's findings were analysed using both regression analysis and the descriptive research approach. The findings of this study indicate that the presence of an adhocratic culture facilitates the process of the knowledge revolution and enhances overall corporate performance, as opposed to clan cultures and hierarchies. Nevertheless, the research extends its analysis beyond financial metrics of organisational efficiency. The present investigation utilised non-financial criteria, including customer and employee satisfaction, resource allocation, service quality, personalised service, and affordability. Due to the potential influence of diverse operationalizations of variables, the generalizability of the present findings is limited.

In their study, Khedhaouria, Nakara, Gharbi, and Bahri (2020) examined the relationship between business orientation, including innovation, risk-taking, and activity, and organisational culture, including adhocracy, clan, hierarchy, and market, and its influence on the success of small firms in Tunisia. The results of the study indicate that entrepreneurship facilitates innovative and prosperous outcomes through fostering adhocracy and market culture, both of which contribute to the success of small businesses. Nevertheless, the analysis reveals a lack of correlation between an adhocracy culture and favourable organisational outcomes. The study replaced a facilitating variable with another variable. The findings of the present study have shown a strong and inseparable connection between the effectiveness of an organisation and the presence of an adhocracy culture within it (Harcourt, Kayii, & Ikegwuru, 2020).

The study conducted by Naranjo-Valencia, Jiménez-Jiménez, and Sanz-Valle in 2016 investigated the interconnectedness of organisational culture, innovation, and competitiveness within Spanish enterprises. The findings of the study indicated that culture can have a varying impact on creativity and organisational performance, depending on the principles it promotes. The adhocratic culture has been identified as the most significant determinant of both creativity and productivity. The findings indicate that the relationship between performance and different organisational culture practises is influenced by the presence of creativity as a mediating factor. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge a theoretical distinction due to the fact that the study was carried out in Spain, a country with a distinct geographical environment in comparison to Kenya. Moreover, this study demonstrates the presence of a moderating variable, rather than establishing a fixed and unchanging influence of organisational culture on productivity and efficiency. This study examined the enduring association between business performance and adhocracy culture.

Misigo, Were, and Odhiambo (2019) conducted a study to examine the impact of adhocracy culture on the performance of public water corporations in Kenya. The correlation coefficient suggests that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between adhering to a particular culture and achieving positive outcomes. The regression analysis reveals that an Adhocratic culture exhibits a slight positive influence on organisational performance, resulting in a productivity increase of 0.327 units. The findings indicate that the presence of a committed community has a substantial influence on the level of success achieved by public water providers in Kenya. The research also focused on providers of potable water. The recent probe focused on hospitality

Original Article

enterprises. Given the different nature of these sectors, it is possible that the results summary may not be appropriate.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the potential link between the independent and dependent variables in this research. The independent variable is the adhocracy culture. The dependent variable is business performance.

Source: Researcher (2023)

Figure 1 demonstrates a 72 percent response rate, with 144 of the 200 surveys issued being completed and returned. 56 of the remaining surveys were either incomplete or not returned. A response rate of greater than 50% is regarded as adequate for analysis. Therefore, the researcher thought that a response of 72% would be sufficient for analysis.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was utilized to evaluate the data tool's reliability. According to Cronbach (1951), the coefficient evaluates the internal consistency or resemblance among the research instrument items. Items with Cronbach Alpha values higher than 0.7 were therefore adopted.

Table 1 indicates the outcome.

Table 1. Reliability Test Results

Variable(N=20)	NoofItems	$\alpha \geq 0.7$	Comment
CorporatePerformance	7	0.905	Reliable
AdhocracyCulture	8	0.834	Reliable

Source: Researcher(2023)

Table 1 demonstrates that adhocracy culture had a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.834 and corporate performance had a value of 0.905. The coefficients were more than 0.7, indicating the reliability of the questionnaire. It's important to remember these benchmarks. There has been much usage of Cronbach Alpha in social science studies. (Kinyua, 2015; Mbugua & Kinyua, 2020; Gatuyu & Kinyua, 2020; Ontita & Kinyua, 2020; Mut himi, Kilika, & Kinyua, 2021; Ong' esa & Kinyua, 2020; King'oo, Kimencu & Kinyua, 2020)

1.1. Descriptive Analysis

The respondents show their agreement with the testimonials relating to corporate performance. Results are presented in Table 2.

Original Article

Table2. Descriptive statistics on corporate performance

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	M	S.D
The services provided at the hotel are of exceptional quality.	2.1%	9.0%	2.8%	40.3%	45.8%	4.19	1.00
The hotel exhibits a high level of professionalism and maintains a commitment to delivering top-quality service.	3.5%	6.2%	6.2%	47.2%	36.8%	4.08	1.00
The hotel provides specialised treatment to patients requiring special attention. Customers express satisfaction with the services provided at the hotel.	2.1%	4.9%	4.2%	35.4%	53.5%	4.33	0.92
The employees demonstrate a strong dedication to their assigned tasks, enabling a heightened emphasis on the delivery	2.8%	2.8%	5.6%	46.5%	42.4%	4.23	0.89
The hotel services can be readily accessed by the local residents.	1.4%	2.8%	4.2%	45.1%	46.5%	4.33	0.80
There exists an operational and effective feedback mechanism aimed at promoting communication with the patients.	3.5%	3.5%	3.5%	43.1%	46.5%	4.26	0.94
Aggregate mean						4.2	0.9

Source: Researcher (2023)

With a mean of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 1.0, the data in Table 2 illustrate that the majority of respondents thought the hotel facility's services were of excellent quality. The respondents once more concurred with the claims that the hotel facility exhibits top-quality professionalism (mean = 4.08, std. dev = 1.0), that it provides specialized service to clients who require special attention (mean=4.33, std. dev=0.92), and that clients are satisfied with the services provided by the hotel (mean=4.23, std. dev=0.89).

The majority of respondents also concurred, stating that employees are committed to their jobs, allowing them to focus on providing excellent service (mean=4.33, std. dev=0.80); the services offered by the hotels are easily accessible to the general public (mean=4.26, std. dev=0.94); and there is an active and useful feedback device to encourage communication with the customers (mean=4.33, std. dev=0.79).The replies on various aspects of business success are supported by an overall mean of 4.25 and a standard deviation of 0.91. This shows that the participants have an understanding of the components of measuring business success. The low degree of consistency indicates that respondents generally agreed with statements made about business performance.

Original Article

The respondents were required to indicate how much of the assertions about the adhocracy culture they agreed with. Table 3 shows the outcome. **Table 3. Descriptive statistics on Adhocracy culture**

Table 3. Descriptive statistics on Adhocracy culture

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	M	S.D
Personnel demonstrate adaptability in response to emerging responsibilities that arise during challenging circumstances.	2.1%	3.5%	1.4%	51.4%	41.7%	4.27	0.83
The hotel has implemented crossfunctional agile teams in order to facilitate organisational transformation.	2.1%	2.1%	3.5%	49.3%	43.1%	4.29	0.81
The operations within the various departments exhibit a high degree of flexibility, thereby accommodating the potential for	2.8%	5.6%	2.8%	45.1%	43.8%	4.22	0.95
The leadership structure exhibits adaptability, enabling the replacement of ineffective leadership with more competent individuals, hence enhancing overall performance.	4.2%	4.9%	0.0%	41.7%	49.3%	4.27	1.00
The hotel promotes the acquisition of new resources.	6.9%	9.0%	3.5%	42.4%	38.2%	3.96	1.19
The leadership fosters a climate that promotes individual initiative in carrying out assigned tasks.	8.3%	13.2 %	2.8%	38.2%	37.5%	3.83	1.29
Aggregate mean						4.13	1.05

The data presented in Table 3 reveals that a majority of the participants agreed with the notion Furthermore, a majority of the participants expressed agreement with the notion that the hotel encourages the acquisition of fresh resources (mean=3.96, standard deviation=1.19). Additionally, the leadership fosters individual creativity in carrying out assigned tasks (mean=4.20, standard deviation=0.98). The organisation also cultivates a distinctive culture that promotes creativity and innovation, resulting in employees feeling at ease when introducing novel ideas related to operational innovation (mean=4.12, standard deviation=1.12).

The findings of this study indicate that the adhocracy culture is characterised by a total score of 4.13 and a variation of 1.05, which aligns with the remarks made on its various components. The suggestion is that the participants had already accepted and adapted to the various elements of adhocracy culture. The slight discrepancy suggests that the participants demonstrated consensus on most features of the adhocracy culture. The results of

Original Article

this study provided empirical evidence for the proposition that the participants possessed a comprehensive understanding of the significance of cultivating an adhocracy culture inside their organisation.

1.2. Inferential Analysis

The study's goal was to determine the impact of Rivers State, Nigeria's adhocracy culture, on the performance of hotels. The study used correlation and regression analysis to achieve the goal.

Correlation Analysis Results

This section presents correlation analysis results on the relationship between adhocracy culture and corporate performance. The findings are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Results

		Corporate performance	Adhocracy Culture
Corporate performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
Adhocracy Culture	Pearson Correlation	.640**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	144	144

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher (2023)

According to Table 4, there is a 0.640 correlation between adhocracy culture and performance. The significant value, which was less than 0.05, was (p = 0.000). This suggests that there was a strong, favorable, and significant relationship between adhocracy culture and performance. This suggests that performance and adhocracy culture are changing in the same way. The results supported the claim made by Yesil and Kaya (2013) that an adherent culture simplifies the knowledge revolution and boosts corporate productivity. This study's findings, however, were in disagreement with those of Khedhaouria, Nakara, Gharbi, and Bahri (2020), who found no connection between adhocracy culture and company performance.

1.2.1. Regression Analysis Results

Regression analysis was performed using simple linear regression analysis. The independent variable (adhocracy culture) was regressed against the dependent variable. The findings are shown in Tables 5, 6 and 7.

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.640a	.409	.405	.30330
a. Predictors: (Constant), adhocracy culture				

Adhocracy culture and company performance have a significant positive linear correlation, as shown by the R-value of 0.640 in Table 5 of this study. R square and adjusted R square values are also similar, coming in at 0.409 and 0.405, respectively, in the findings. As a consequence, the constructed statistical model's explanatory power, as measured by the updated coefficient of multiple determination, is 0.405. This indicates that 41% of hotel performance is attributable to the adhocracy culture.

Original Article

Table 6. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.049	1	9.049	98.372	.000b
	Residual	13.063	142	.092		
	Total	22.112	143			

Table 6 shows that the established statistical model fit the observed data well, with an F statistic of 98.372 at a 0.000 level of significance less than the 0.05 threshold. The results indicated that the proposed model predicted the dependent variable with statistical significance (excellent fit).

Table 7. Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.261	.302		4.173	.000
	Adhocracy culture	.719	.072	.640	9.918	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Corporate performance

Model

Corporate performance = 1.261 + 0.719 Adhocracy Culture

The goal of this study was to examine how an adherent culture affected a hotel's performance. The outcomes showed that the adhocracy culture has a good and significant impact on business performance. A beta of 0.719 and a p-value of 0.000 support this. The p value with a 95% confidence interval is less than 0.05. According to the findings, a hotel's performance would alter by 0.719 if its adhocracy culture were to change. The research's conclusions agreed with those made by Naranjo-Valencia, Jiménez-Jiménez, and Sanz-Valle (2016), who claimed that adhocratic cultures are the greatest in foretelling creativity and productivity. Misigo, Were, and Odhiambo (2019) revealed similar findings showing an adherent culture had a beneficial influence on organizational effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

The study sheds valuable light on the intricate relationship between organizational culture and corporate performance in the specific context of the Nigerian hotel industry. The findings suggest that an adhocracy culture, characterized by flexibility, innovation, and adaptability, can positively impact the performance of hotels in Rivers State. This underscores the importance of fostering a culture of creativity and empowerment within the industry to navigate dynamic and competitive environments effectively. However, it is imperative for hotel management in the region to strike a balance between adhocracy and stability to ensure sustained success. Further research and practical strategies for cultivating adhocracy culture can contribute to the growth and resilience of the hotel sector in Rivers State, Nigeria

RECOMMENDATIONS

The management of hotels should see to it that policies are revised to strengthen the elements of the corporation's adhocracy culture. More specifically, the management should stimulate independent efforts and promote adaptation. By acquiring new resources, the management should further grow the businesses' resources.

Original Article

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Original Article

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